

Emotions-based interactions: Design challenges for increasing well-being

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Abstract How to drive everyday life toward creativity and a positive state of mind? Can interaction design trigger emotions and reinforce well-being attitude? This paper is a first exploratory study of design research, trends and practices on how devices and interfaces could advance when engaging more deeply with the recognition of emotions. The purpose is to provide insights and resources across different perspectives for the understanding of the emerging landscape of emotion-based technologies and on how it can evolve with future interfaces involving well-being intent. The role of emotions in the design has been growing, this paper gathers the preliminary approaches to frame drivers that influence the design, especially dealing with new directions and visions to address well-being. Finally, it outlines some of challenges and future research opportunities.

Keywords *Interaction design, Positive emotions, Experience design, Emotional well-being, Future interfaces*

Introduction

In the pursuit of well-being this paper offers an exploratory study for framing the growing field of emotion-based technologies and describes futures research opportunities and challenges that might drive interaction design.

The vision that emotions can become input for the next future interactive systems and interfaces is fueled by the ongoing proliferation of sensor-based technologies that can recognize the peoples' emotional states. One of the key challenge in those system is the real-time tracking of emotions and the ability to relate them to behavioural data.

This open up a new territory with respect to the design of interactive interfaces able to drive pervasive sensitive systems in triggering positive emotions and, as core consequence, in improving well-being.

Why integrating positive emotions into the interaction design process?

Emotions are spontaneous and almost irrational reactions to external stimuli, in this manner they are naturally interactive overwhelming the human body which responds through various signals, physical and behavioural manifestations. Behavioural manifestations of emotions include various decision-making processes: consumption choices (Brandt, 2016), the perceived quality of social relationships (Reeves and Nass, 1996), effort and time used to interact with media and information technologies (Zhang, 2008) as well as about the state of mind habits.

Working with Positive Emotions, as fundamental component of the theory of well-being (Seligman, 2011) is the key to design meaningful experiences and to increase life satisfaction, because cognitive system

learns from experiences and provides an adaptive reaction.

The implications of enhancing personal well-being toward an upward spiral in increasing positive emotions (Friedrickson, 2002), are related to several aspects that affect human psychology such as motivation, self-esteem, creativity, competence, trust, achievement, gratification and so on. Trigger positive emotions is a practical method that can help to release hemic disorders of the information society such as stress, anxiety and depression. Moreover, experiencing positive emotions can optimize psychological resilience and increase health benefits and even longevity (Ekman, 2003). These findings indicate a reciprocal connection among design research, psychology, social science and behavioural change perspective that outlines the great complexity of defining new tool and methodologies (Sanders, 1999) to design interfaces that facilitate positive people's life experiences.

While much of technological advancement within emotion recognition borrowed its theoretical framework from cognitive psychology to analyse and drive emotions conveyed by products, the social sciences within interactive systems were slower to suggest new applications. This common ground could help designer and researchers to access the emotional experience in a way that would improve well-being.

How to building the emotional connection between people and new form of interfaces is part of the design research advancement (Yagou, 2006). In this framework this research aims to outlines possible directions to address the interaction design for emotional well-being.

Background and related work

The psychologist Paul Ekman (2003) argues that there are two steps to improve our emotional life. One is to be aware of emotions, learn to read them and recognize their expression, the second step is to realize when we are responding emotionally, reactions and situations. This awareness can increase the gap between impulse and action to stimulus. In the same way interaction design processes can follow this path activating emotional experiences and self-awareness through new solutions.

We could be inspired by the term 'positive' as a way to focus on the mechanism to encourage cognition and action toward meaningful individual improvements, building optimism, for instance, increase self-esteem, energize goal-achievement.

Positive psychology movement has grown quickly in the last 15 years. It is the scientific understanding of the conditions and processes that contribute to the flourishing or optimal functioning of people, groups and institutions (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000, Reeve, 2014).

According to Fredrickson's broaden-and-build theory (2001), positive emotions - including amusement, interest, joy, contentment, pride in achievement, love, interest, satisfaction, sensory pleasure - encourage people's exploration thought actions. Play for instance, is an activity that helps balancing physical, intellectual and social skills that fuels creative thinking development and the ability of learning (Callois, 1958). Phenomenologically all positive emotions share the ability to build people's personal resources and culture by creating the urge to explore, taking in new experiences and expanding the self in the process. Although positive emotions can be valued as subjective experiences that occur in specific circumstances, they move individuals toward a better mindset developing cognitive skills essential to well-being. Courage, happiness, motivation, engagement, self-esteem, hope as well as wisdom, forgiveness are all individual traits that trigger our own emotional responses that turn colors to our interpretation of actions, situations and relationships (Ekman, 2002).

More recently, Martin Seligman (2011) provides the PERMA conceptual model of well-being that consists in five elements: (1) positive emotions, (2) engagement, (3) positive relationships with others, (4) meaning and purpose to belong a part of something bigger than themselves, and (5) accomplishment that is the sense of achievement. Those five measurable elements could help individuals find paths to flourishing.

However life satisfaction has different life status variables, called 'circumstances' (cultural, political and economical situations) that influence peoples' well-being (Seligman 2016; Helliwell, 2016). In recent years, the engagement nature of interactive technologies has offered new possibilities in the area of intentional activities (Lyubomirsky, 2006) that are actions and practices that people choose to engage and invest effort to enact.

Emotions, from amusement to awe, interest, gratitude, curiosity and fear, are studied and applied in combination to other media, entertainment, interactive products and game design. XEODesign conducted several research studies on how computers and video games trigger emotions. Using facial expression analysis Nicole Lazzaro and team (2004) measured player's emotional responses identifying over thirty emotions. The experiences the game creates provide enjoyment, engagement, motivation, fun and altered state. The observation of facial gestures, body language and verbal comments revealed also excitement, frustration amusement as well as sensory pleasure derived from a rich experience of digital playing. Playing with games, we can experience the three kinds of positive emotions highlighted by Seligman (2011): (1) pleasure and gratification, (2) embodiment of strengths and virtues and (3) meaning and purpose. Interestingly, these same powerful traits create the contexts through which people are motivated in pursuing their goals, training their skills and in making their choices within an activity context (Weiser et al. 2015). Face and body expressions are crucial to the development of future interactive interfaces for well-being because they are not only display of emotions but generates beliefs and contribute to improve successful engagement and purpose.

Emotions and interactions

At their juncture, emotions and interaction design can play a very important role in improving the quality of life. Some studies on game design field suggest that emotions can be an important resource that interaction design cannot ignore as they move people to be proactive (McGonigal, 2011).

To date, design has engaged with emotions that show some cognitive characteristics of those involved on how people frame their relationship with objects, devices and others. Norman (2004) defines this emotional interaction with objects as visceral, behavioral and/or reflective. Those three correspondent design levels reveal also the personality of a product mediating behaviours across space and networks. Thus, consumers are led to choose their own interactive services and objects based on those experience. Gaver (1999) argues that emotion is a subset of the irrational in the design of technologies. Every artifact conveys emotions from users since the interaction with them implies spontaneity, intuition and elicit cultural connotations. However, rather than pursuing a computational approach to emotions, Gaver (2009) has also discussed a broader view of interaction design in which emotional experiences become the outcomes of people's engagement. In fact, enjoyment, motivation and sense of achievement are among the most desired experiences in interacting with digital games and playful artifacts. Furthermore autonomy, competence and relatedness are also innate psychological needs which lead to spontaneous players' emotional investment (Deterding, 2015).

These reciprocal relations among positive emotions, design and well-being need a wider systemic perspective. Hence, the influence of emotions on the

design of interfaces is not restricted to one source of experience - leisure, communication, marketing - but also it might be of interest exploring multiple sources for instance self-consciousness circumstances, or contexts to encourage behavioral change or to suggest sustainable living practices. For example design can drive positive emotional responses derived by the interaction with a system of connected objects ables to stimulate conversation, creativity and personal growth.

Many smart applications are already on this path pursuing several objective: training for self-awareness and healthy nutrition (Jiyo), meditation (Headspace), positive attitude (Uplifted), positive relationship (Couple), stress management (Empatica).

Design provides interconnectivity that is the potential of recent HCI and sustainability related research. Prototypes are starting to embed emotions in a variety of new sensing technologies often associated with the Internet of Things (IoT) vision (Koreshoff et. al, 2013), pervasive, ubiquitous and affective computing. Equipped with sensing technologies, interconnected interfaces can finely track behaviors and contexts promoting well-being and collective awareness through sharing and behavior change support (Castri, 2014).

This rapidly growing of pervasive sensing technologies can move interaction design to extend the benefits of emotional engagement in the direction of well-being.

Table 1 shows a summary of the relevant emotions-related research efforts mentioned. The various domains, focus and influences could be extended to new domains from arts to humanity covering new areas such as public, urban environments and domestic contexts which may address the interplay of techniques in developing interfaces able to interact with people's emotions and possible desires.

Emotions-based interfaces

In humans, emotions entail distinctive, integrated, and intimate ways of interacting, they impact on individual's everyday experiences, decision making, feelings, interpersonal relationships and behaviors. The understanding of what emotional triggers are, is

the core also of advertising effectiveness and media environment design and distribution. However there is a wide research area in developing technologies ables to handle data related to emotions. Face is the preeminent medium of emotional expression detection, but also speech patterns, body gestures and physiological reaction to stimuli are starting to be tracked and analyzed by computing systems.

On one hand, the accuracy of sensors and tracking systems are becoming sharper and intelligent. Cameras and microphones can detect facial or voices expressions and infer emotional state to a system database. It is the case of the commercial product Emotient (2016), an automatic and real-time detection system for objects analysis, in particular faces and muscles movements and attitudes prediction. This technology detects and measures mood, stress, sentiments, gender and age witnessing for the first time an expansion of emotion analytics capabilities in different sectors including automotive, medical technology and market research.

On the other hand affective computer systems are seeking to identify human emotional states and correlating physiological responses. Beyond detection of such changes in skin temperature, perspiration, heartbeat or nervous system signals, these bio-modules are often embedded in wearable devices - such as Affectiva measurement technology (Swinton, 2012) - enabling the emotional impact analysis. As a consequence, emotional data retrieved could act as input to change interfaces behaviors in response to user's emotional expression and trigger an incremental process.

Although some new relationships between technologies and emotions are still evolving, they can have implications in design and functions allowed.

The fast moving consumer goods industry connected to emotions measurements technologies shows a growing interest to understand how emotions affect our decisions making process to buy, be motivated and interact (Brandt, 2016). The early real-time prototype of Fraunhofer (2012), for instance, enables the detection of four families of emotions that are happiness, anger, sadness and surprise. Their technology has been already combined in Google Glass

Table 1. Research areas involved in emotions and design.

Domain	Area of focus	Influences
Positive Psychology	Positive emotions, meaning, happiness and flow, psychological resilience	Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi (2000), Fredrickson (2001, 2002), Reeve (2014), Lyubomirsky (2005)
Affective computing	Bi-directional communication, Bio-metrics, sensing	Picard (2001), Kanjo, Al-Husain and Chamberlain (2015)
Design and Entertainment	Disruptive purposive, play, product interaction design and ambiguity	Lazzaro (2004), Fogg (2009), Gaver (2009), McGonigal (2011), Deterding (2015)
Neuroscience	Conscious and non-conscious user responses, emotions measurement and motivation, emotional design	Ekman (2003), Norman (2004)
IoT and ICT	Haptic interactions, connections of interfaces, networks,	Koreshoff (2011), Zhang (2008)

demonstrating how wearable devices can be used to distinguish different types of emotional expressions in natural settings. What foreground this phenomenon of pervasive sensing technologies is the issue of quantitative measure the emotional experiences of individuals.

Further, quantitative data is going to be related to user behaviour analyzing context and conditions in which experiences affect emotional well-being. For example, Neumitra (2016) application links the user's stress level to their social mediated activities giving personalized feedback.

Early in 2002, the call for a design change went out, and the Affective Computing Research Group (Picard, 2002) has argued that human-computer interaction is social and emotional and as technology is changing, more designers can consider new points of views integrating interfaces to facilitate emotional and social communication. Now, the Affective Computing field embraces the approach that human-computer interaction should recognize and responds to user's emotions in a way that helps users meet their needs with emotionally supportive interactions (Picard, 2001).

Proceeding from this point, the design of technologies can extend these theoretical findings to produce significant results. What if self-esteem, happiness, motivation, engagement reactions become important keys to address the development of next future interfaces systems? Key to connect these approaches is the integration of positive emotion research in programming interfaces. Together with verbal, facial or gestures recognition tools interaction design is a reliable way to move the emotion analytics toward something that can generate important personal data resources for promoting well-being and supporting positive experiences. While commercial products are going to cover a broader range of domains, we can imagine future systems that can learn from humans' emotions encouraging people making better choices for their life. The reciprocal relation among design and emotions affecting each other will shape next future behaviors.

Designing for emotional well-being

Although there is still no comprehensive definition for emotional-based interfaces, emotions emerge in the design process as a real quality of the intentional interactions between humans and interfaces.

Emotions are important motivational triggers that energize and direct behaviors (Zhang, 2008; Fogg 2009). Working with those motivational lens is also an important and powerful source in providing guidance to ICT design as tools for understanding factors that lead a behavior shift into happiness and well-being attitudes.

Positive intentions cannot exist just at an abstract level. Here we approach the definition of the emotional drivers by mapping the core features into a circular structure (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Mapping emotional drivers and factors contributing to well-being.

The approaches reviewed in this study show a broad canvas of emotions. The revealed emotions are associated with six factors that influence well-being in the daily life: optimism, creative thinking, resilience, positive relationship, self-esteem and engagement.

The map is an insight guidance for HCI designers. That is, increasing their effort in exploring users' emotions through playful interfaces, designers should understand how to interact through them with a certain amount of flexibility - and invisibility - and better fulfill moods, attitudes and individual preferences.

Good responsible design shows a clear expansion of the technology advancement and a transformation of processes for a sustainable change.

Accordingly to the primary question addressed in this article: through what challenges can design include emotions to increase the well-being level, some movements can be defined across a number of disciplinary dimensions. Those provide clues into some of the factors that predicts future developments.

- *Sensing devices: environmental or wearable interfaces, either unobtrusive, pervasive and invisible. A more deep integration of cognitive and emotional data resources into systems able to read emotional processes and understand their circumstances.*
- *Models of well-being: development of open-ended sensing prototypes to observe patterns of positive behaviours and train people response-ability skills. This design-driven approach supports the analysis of emotional feelings related to daily life experiences.*
- *Adaptative tools: a broader combination of techniques and methodologies to read variance in emotions and be able to reply in a meaningful way. These allow people to elicit their emotions*

and to increase their self-awareness process for an emotional well-being enhancement.

- *Networked experiences: take into account the opportunity people have to share their emotions. This means considering links among biometric data, interaction environments and daily life behaviours. And more bridge those data at social level through networked media.*

Nowadays, the tendency is to prototype applications to train self-awareness, next step is to combine these with automatic emotional sensing technologies to promote adaptive contexts based on personal data resources. A step further is to design broaden thought-action social environments direct to support individual growth and social transformation.

While various techniques and tracking tools are growing toward improving quantitative measurement, new systems are starting to connect emotional data with users habits at both individual and social layers. IoT prototypes and new wearable connected devices could be a support accompanying a sustainable change in mediating well-being.

Conclusions

This research aims at overcoming the design approach to draw emotional motivation towards products, goods and services, suggesting interaction design to include emotions-based technologies as part of the next future interfaces ecosystem.

The model encompass a wide variety of findings and suggests a number of new directions. Investigating emotional-based interaction various design approaches and research communities become engaged together encouraging well-being perspective. Advances in sensing technologies development, user experience and positive psychology have opened up practical ways to further include emotion-related human aspects into the design process.

In this landscape design and in particular interaction design, has the opportunity to support people's proactive experiences, enhance emotional well-being and, as consequence, improve the quality of life. Incorporating emotions into the design work means to add another level into the practice and then considering three aspects of the project: one is the technology to read, interpret and adapt to humans' emotions, the second is the behavioural level and what is connected to people's activities, believe system, daily life and experiences to use products and interfaces and the third is the emotional level and what moves people to act, to growth and to connect each other through different languages and media. It is finally time for the issue of emotional interaction design to be given the attention that it deserve for developing next future environments and interfaces towards well-being.

The question of how to create the relations between emotional well-being and design, as manifested in this research, embraces a long-term vision of integrating different perspectives and needs further expansion. We come together with Design and Emotion

community to present this exploration and invite a dialog regarding next future progresses.

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